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Perception on Environmental Issues in Relation to the Pro Environmental Behaviour and Environmental Concerns of Secondary Level Teacher Trainees

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to find out the "Perception on Environmental Issues in Relation to the Pro Environmental Behaviour and Environmental Concerns of Secondary Level Teacher Trainees " For this study 1774 secondary level teacher trainees selected through stratified random sampling technique from government, government aided and private institution of education in Dharmapuri, Krishnagiri, Salem, Vellore and Thiruvannamalai districts. The self-developed Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The current study shows that the level of environmental issues, pro-environmental behaviour, and environmental concern. As the result obtained by the analysis of data, it has been found that, female secondary level teacher trainees scored higher mean scores and differ significantly with the male trainees, the reason may be that female have high level of concern, motherhood character, patients, more health conscious and moreover they are very careful while using any type of resources than male trainees.

INTRODUCTION

Plastics are organic polymers of high molecular mass and often contain other substances. They are usually synthetic, mainly derived from petrochemicals. Due to their low cost, ease of manufacture, versatility, non-corrosiveness and imperviousness to water, plastics are used for multiple purposes at different scales. Plastic was invented in New York in 1907 by Leo Baekeland. Further, many chemists, including Nobel laureate Hermann Staudinger (father of polymer chemistry) and Herman Mark (father of polymer physics), have contributed to the materials science of plastics. However, these scientists could not have anticipated such an exponential growth of plastic production. Most plastic products are lightweight, inexpensive, and durable. These defining characteristics make plastics a convenient material for the manufacture of everyday products. However, these same attributes make plastics a threat to ecosystems. It affects the environment, eco systems, bio diversity, cause to climate change, global warming etc.

In simple words Plastic usage and wastages do not get decompose easily, settles down in the earth that leads to increase in the mass of waste in the soil. It affects the water cycle by disturbing the rainwater to enter into the land as the water and air cannot pass through it. Initially it show decrease in ground water level and it leads to so many environmental issues. Even it sometimes causes death of animals due to the intake of plastic. The cost for recycling the plastic is very high and almost it is a loss process. The half-life period for plastic is too long that it takes some millions of

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years to decay. The production of plastic with lower number of microns is very cheap; unfortunately lower the microns in the plastic lower the chance to get decompose.

While the issue of plastic pollution in aquatic environments (marine and freshwater) has been gaining increasing attention, the problem of plastic contamination in the terrestrial environment has remained widely unexplored. Plastic pollution may be more dramatically seen in the oceans; however, more than 80% of the plastics found in marine environments has been produced, consumed and disposed of in land. Therefore, plastic pollution in soil is a problem both of contamination and damage to terrestrial environments and of transfer to aquatic systems.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

We are human beings mainly depending on the ecosystem for our survival. Due to increasing population, the human need more natural resources for their survival in this earth. Continuous use of these resources leads to a scarcity of natural resources. To prevent the overused and damaged environment for the future generation is important. Creating awareness about environmental issues is exigencies in today's scenario. Humans and other organisms have equal rights to live in this ecosystem. Most of the species are disappeared due to the undesirable activity of the human alone. Most of the marine organisms are affected by plastic and e-waste pollution. Gradually they are going too vanished out from our ecosystem which affects the equilibrium and the food chain. Every individual has responsibility for protecting nature not only for the future generation also for the other animals and plants which are the part of an ecosystem.

Environmental issues cannot prevent only by the law itself. The behaviour of an individual plays a vital role in preventing the environment. Knowledge about the environment is very important and also their attitude plays a significant effect on the environment. Positive attitudes towards the environment decrease environmental issues. Citizens of every nation have the responsibility to produce the ecosystem especially the teachers who are educating the future generation. Hence the present study deals with the perception of environmental issues in relation to their pro-environmental behaviour and environmental concern.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Ficko, A., & Bončina, A., (2018) investigated the future teacher's attitude towards environmental pollution. Pre-primary and primary teacher trainees were taken as a sample from the university of Granada, Spain. The results showed that gender had no significant difference in the attitude towards pollution. The participants showed high concern and attitude towards environmental pollutions. The researcher suggested including environmental education as the main subject from the primary level to the college level.

Mohammadi, M., (2018) explained the causes and remedial measures of plastic pollution in the marine region. The researcher explained in detail about plastic pollution like city garbage, industrial wastes, tourism disposal, and commercial fishing nets. Due to the pollution the marine ecosystem disturbed by an increase in the disappearing of rare species, reproduction problems, internal organs damaged and so on. The researcher suggested various strategies like increasing the production of bio-degradable products, chemical recycling, and pyrolysis to overcome the plastic pollution in the marine regions.

Duan W & Sheng J., (2018) examined Chinese individual's environmental knowledge transfer into pro-environmental behaviour. The findings clearly explain the dwelling environmental knowledge and pollution perceptions are the stronger predictors and additional variances. The dwelling environmental perception had a higher significance than public pro-environmental behaviour.

TITLE OF THE STUDY

The problem took for the present study is “**Perception on Environmental Issues in Relation to the Pro Environmental Behaviour and Environmental Concerns of Secondary Level Teacher Trainees** “

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

Environmental Issues

The harmful effect and undesirable changes created by the human to the environment are known as environmental issues. Most of the undesirable changes are created by the human due to advanced development and industrialization. The environmental issues are increasing day by day. The natural non-renewable resources are overused and there is nothing left over for the future generation. The plastic and E-waste pollutions are very high in peak. In the present study, the environmental issues are the plastic pollution and E-waste pollution viz, awareness, management, and disposal.

Pro-Environmental Behaviour

Human behaviour which tends to reduce the negative impact on the environment and also for the betterment of the environment is known as pro-environmental behaviour. Human behaviour plays an important role for every action performed by the individuals. The behaviour reflects how the individual interact with the environment. It shows that whether they show environmental friendly behaviour towards the environment. From the behavioural outcomes we can find out their environmental behaviours. Environmental knowledge, environmental attitude, conservation of resources behaviour, environmental citizen behaviour, and environmentally aware consumer behaviour these are the five dimensions of pro-environmental behaviour included in the present study.

Environmental Concerns

Environmental concern refers to how the individual shows their concern towards themselves, with their family members, their future generation, all the human beings, animal kingdom and so on. The individual have the responsibility to protect the nature around them. It shows the relationship exist between the human and environment. Egoistic concern, altruistic concern, and biospheric concerns are the dimensions include in environmental concern.

Secondary Level Teacher Trainees

A secondary level teacher trainee refers to those who are studying two years bachelor of education programme (B.Ed.) degree. The student teachers after completion of two years are expected to become as a teacher. During the period of course the student teachers are trained by various innovative practices, knowledge, curriculum, teaching and learning skills, and so on to become a best teacher..

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study were as follows:

- To find the differences in perception on environmental issues of secondary level teacher trainees

- To study the differences in pro-environmental behaviour of secondary level teacher trainees
- To investigate the differences in the environmental concerns of secondary level teacher trainees

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The hypotheses of the present study are as follows

- There is no significant difference in the perception on environmental issues of secondary level teacher trainees based on the select sub samples
- There is no significant difference in the pro-environmental behaviour of secondary level teacher trainees based on the select sub-samples
- There is no significant difference in the environmental concerns of secondary level teacher trainees based on the select sub-samples

METHODOLOGY

For the present study normative survey method was adopted. The sample size consists of 1774 secondary level teacher trainees selected through stratified random sampling technique from government, government aided and private institution of education in Dharmapuri, Krishnagiri, Salem, Vellore and Thiruvannamalai districts.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

For the present study the following tools were developed by the investigator along with the personal data sheet.

1. Environmental Issues Scale (EIS)
2. Pro - Environmental Behaviour Scale (PEBS)
3. Environmental Concerns Scale (ECS)

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Statistical measures such as Mean, SD and t-tests were used to interpret the obtained data.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Environmental Issues

- Female secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (125.40) than male secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees who are settled in the village have higher mean scores (126.60) than the city and town settled secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Krishnagiri district secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (144.50) than the other district secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Firstborn secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (126.50) than the middle, last and single born secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees who are studying in government colleges have higher mean scores (140.10) than the government-aided and private secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. The second year secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (127.73) than the first year secondary level teacher trainees issues. Married secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (134.62) than the single secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees

who are studied M.Phil and other qualification have higher mean scores (137.64) than the UG and PG degree secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees belong to science as a stream of study have higher mean scores (129.91) than the arts secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees who are studying environmental as a subject have higher mean scores (127.73) than the studied secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees who are interested in the environmental subject have higher mean scores (128.31) than that of not interested secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees who are organized environmental awareness programmes have higher mean scores (136.36) than the attended and not attended secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Eco-club members of secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (134.34) than that of a non-member of secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues. Secondary level teacher trainees whose family monthly income are above 30,000 have higher mean scores (133.42) than below income level of secondary level teacher trainees in environmental issues.

It is revealed that,

- Male and female secondary level teacher trainees differ in their PPA, PPM, PP dimensions and global total of environmental issues.
- There is an interaction among the secondary level teacher trainees in different places of settlement and their dimensions PPA, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPM, EWPD and global total of environmental issues.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different districts and their dimensions of plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP, and global EI.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees based on birth order and their dimensions PPA, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP and global total of EI.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees with different type of institution and their dimensions plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP, and global EI.
- First year and Second year secondary level teacher trainees differ in their PPA, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.
- Single and married secondary level teacher trainees differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in a different type of educational qualification and their dimensions plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP, and global EI.
- Arts stream and science stream secondary level teacher trainees differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.
- Environmental science as a subject studied and studying secondary level teacher trainees differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.
- Secondary level teacher trainees interested in the environmental subject and not interested differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP dimensions, and global environmental issues.

- There is an interaction between the awareness programs of secondary level teacher trainees and their dimensions of plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP, and global EI.
- Eco club members and non member of secondary level teacher trainees differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.
- Parental income above and below 30,000 secondary level teacher trainees differ in their plastic pollution awareness, PPM, PPD, PP, EWPA, EWPM, EWPD, EWP of dimensions and global environmental issues.

PRO-ENVIRONMENTAL BEHAVIOUR

- Female secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (128.48) than male secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees live in the village have higher mean scores (129.05) than the city and town settled secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Krishnagiri district secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (143.56) than the other district secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Firstborn secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (130.56) than the middle, last and single secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees who are studying in government colleges have higher mean scores (142.80) than the government-aided and private secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. The second year secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (131.44) than the first year secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Married secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (136.45) than the single secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees who are qualified M.Phil and others have higher mean scores (138.91) than the UG and PG degree in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees belong to science as a stream of study have higher mean scores (132.26) than the arts secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees who are studying environmental as a subject have higher mean scores (131.44) than the studied secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees who are interested in the environmental subject have higher mean scores (131.61) than that of not interested secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees who are organized environmental awareness programmes have higher mean scores (140.58) than the attended and not attended secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Eco-club members of secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (138.47) than that of a non-member of secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour. Secondary level teacher trainees whose family monthly income are above ₹30,000 have higher mean scores (137.46) than below income level of secondary level teacher trainees in pro-environmental behaviour.

It is shown that,

- Male and female secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions of PEB.
- There is no interaction between the EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB among the secondary level teacher trainees in different places of settlement.

- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different districts and their EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees based on birth order and their EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different types of institution and their dimensions EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimension and global total of PEB.
- First year and Second year secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- Single and married secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees with different educational qualification and their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- Arts stream and science stream secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- Environmental science as a subject studied and studying secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- Secondary level teacher trainees interested in the environmental subject and not interested differ in their EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions and global total of PEB.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees environmental related awareness programmes and their EK, EA, CRB, ECB, EACB dimensions and global score of PEB.
- Eco club member and non member secondary level teacher trainees differ in their in EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global score of PEB.
- Parental income above 30,000 and below 30,000 of secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EK, EA, CRB, EACB dimensions and global score of PEB

ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS

- Female secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (82.73) than male secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees settled in the city have higher mean scores (83.16) than the town and village settled secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Vellore district secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (83.59) than the other district secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Firstborn secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (84.65) than the middle, last and single born secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees who are studying in government colleges have higher mean scores (86.35) than the government-aided and private secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. The second year secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (84.76) than the first year secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Married secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (86.62) than the single secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees who are qualified M.Phil and others have higher mean scores (90.96) than the UG and PG degree secondary level teacher trainee's environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees belong to science as a stream of study have higher mean scores (85.23) than the arts secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees studying environmental as a subject have higher

mean scores (84.76) than the studied secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees who are interested in the environmental subject have higher mean scores than that of not interested in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees who are organized environmental awareness programmes have higher mean scores (84.41) than the attended and not attended secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Eco-club members of secondary level teacher trainees have higher mean scores (89.50) than that of non-member of secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern. Secondary level teacher trainees whose family monthly income are above 30,000 have higher mean scores (87.60) than below income level of secondary level teacher trainees in environmental concern.

It is revealed that,

- Male and female secondary level teacher trainees differ in their AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different places of settlement and their ACE dimension of EC.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different districts and their EEC dimension and global total of EC.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees based on birth order and their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in different types of institution and their EEC, AEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- First year and Second year secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- Single and married secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- There is an interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees in a different type of educational qualification and their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- Arts stream and science stream secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- Environmental science as a subject studied and studying secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC,
- Secondary level teacher trainees interested in the environmental subject and not interested differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- There is interaction between the secondary level teacher trainees and their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- Eco club member and non member secondary level teacher trainees differ in their in EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.
- Parental income above and below 30,000 of secondary level teacher trainees differ in their EEC, AEC, BEC dimensions and global total of EC.

CONCLUSION

The present study aimed to find out the perception of environmental issues concerning the pro-environmental behaviour and environmental concern of secondary level teacher trainees. The findings of present study reveals that, the secondary level teacher trainees who are taking science as a stream of study, studying environmental education as a paper, interested in environmental subjects, attended and organized environmental related awareness programmes, being a member

of the environmental club has a significant difference in environmental awareness, management, disposal, pro-environmental behaviour, and environmental concern compared with their counterparts. The reason may be that the trainees have studied basic environmental related concepts hence they understand and implement theoretical knowledge in to practice and also the eco-club member and awareness programmes empower the students by participate meaningful activities to the society hence they show eco-friendly and positive behaviour. Compare to plastic pollution the teacher trainees shows low level of awareness, management and disposal on e-waste pollution consequently arise need to increase awareness regarding e-waste. From the results, it is clear that the persuasive need and importance of environmental education and environmental related awareness and programmes should be increased for the secondary level teacher trainees because they have the responsibility to educate the future upcoming responsible citizens of our Indian nation. The secondary level teacher trainees who are going to impart the environmental knowledge, concepts, and awareness to their subsequent generations to rise environmentally motivated citizens for our sustainable environment.

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